

METHODS FOR DEVELOPING MOTOR ABILITIES OF GIRLS 6-7 YEARS OF AGE IN ACCENTED LESSONS

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The article presents the results of a pedagogical experiment to improve the motor abilities of 6-7 year old girls in physical education lessons with the introduction of an accentuated methodology for aimed at increasing the level of their physical status.

Key words: Accented methodology , monitoring, motor readiness, standard, correlation, test, functional training

Improving the quality of education is one of the pressing problems of pedagogical science of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the solution of which is closely related to the modernization of the content of education and the optimization of pedagogical technologies in the educational process. (5.7)

The process of physical education in secondary schools, on the basis of which children 's interest in engaging in selected types of children's sports is formed and provides for the creation of a basis for basic physical training, the formation of a fund of motor skills and abilities in order to experimentally substantiate effective means, forms and methods of training physical qualities.

To address issues of intensifying the process of physical education, many authors (1.2.3.) propose the use of selectively targeted physical activity during sensitive periods in the development of their motor abilities, which is the most favorable period for a targeted impact on their physical abilities.

Annual monitoring of the motor readiness of children admitted to school revealed a relatively low satisfactory level of physical status, which creates problems for the coaching staff of children's sports schools conducting professional selection of children for children's sports.

In order to solve these problems, it seemed interesting to identify the level of physical development of girls in the first year of study in the school education system.

The organization of the experiment was based on the scheme of comparative pedagogical research with the participation of control and experimental groups,

where first-graders from two secondary schools took part; the results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Indicators of physical development of girls in the first year of school

Age years	N	Body length (cm)	Body weight (kg)	OGK (cm)
6	26	111.5±4.6	19.8±1.9	56.8±3.9
7	32	117.8±4.9	21.7±1.7	61.1±3.3

In the experimental groups, in agreement with the pedagogical leadership of the schools, daily physical education and sports activities and accentuated physical education lessons were conducted by graduate students of the Faculty of Physical Education who were on teaching practice at this school. In the educational process , a developed author's program was introduced, aimed at improving motor qualities in girls, with constant pedagogical and medical monitoring of physical activity tolerance with testing of motor qualities at the end of each quarter throughout the school year.

Monitoring analysis revealed that during the experiment the level of somatometric characteristics of the studied girls in the experimental group increased significantly to a statistically significant level. Thus, body length, which reflects the nature of the formation of the child’s body and tends to significantly increase annually, in girls increased by 6.3 cm (P<0.01), while it was revealed that body weight by 7 years of age increases in relation to 6 years of age on average by 1.9 kg (P<0.01). By the end of the experiment, the chest circumference increased from 56,8 cm61.1 cm and amounted to a difference of 4.3 cm, (P<0.01), (4.6)

An important pedagogical task of physical education is to increase the level of motor preparedness of children. Without knowledge of the initial levels of development of the motor abilities of a growing organism, it is impossible to evaluate the results of targeted pedagogical activities and subsequently plan the process of improving their motor abilities.

In this regard, a monitoring analysis of the motor readiness of children in the first year of school was carried out in quarters, where the battery of tests was borrowed from the state standards for physical education; the test results are presented in Table 2 .

Analysis of the initial indicators revealed that 30 mthe girls covered the distance in 7.2 ±0.5 seconds on average . The physical quality of agility was assessed

according to the 3 x 10m shuttle run test, where the result for girls was 10.9 ± 0.6 seconds. Accented activities carried out during the pedagogical experiment made it possible to increase girls' results by 6.5%

table 2

Annual dynamics of motor readiness of girls 6-7 years old

No.	Tests	H E T I N E R T A N D										
		I		II		%	III		%	IV		%
		$\bar{X}$	σ	$\bar{X}$	σ		$\bar{X}$	σ		$\bar{X}$	σ	
1	Running 30 m. With.	7.2	0.5	7.1	0.6	1.4	6.8	0.7	5.6	6.7	0.6	7.1
2	Long jump s \ m, cm.	99.2	11.0	102.1	10.9	2.9	112.4	11.7	11.8	114.6	11.9	13.5
3	Throwing a tennis ball m.	10.4	3.4	11.6	3.2	10.4	12.8	3.9	18.8	13.6	3.5	23.6
4	Flexion and extension of arms, times	4.0	1.1	4.3	0.9	4.7	5.1	1.2	11.6	5.2	1.1	22.1
5	Shuttle run 3x10 m.s.	10.9	0.6	10.8	0.7	1.0	10.4	0.6	4.6	10.2	0.7	6.5
6	Raising the body, once	7.3	3.1	7.6	2.8	4.0	9.1	3.2	19.8	9.2	3.2	20.7

Repeated testing of speed qualities at the end of the second quarter in groups of girls revealed a tendency towards a slight improvement of 0.1 seconds (1.4%) ($p > 0.05$).

Throughout the entire third quarter, where athletics and games lessons predominated, the girls' speed performance indicators increased significantly to 6.8 ± 0.7 seconds. (5.6%). Repeated studies at the end of the school year revealed that the speed capabilities of the girls studied significantly improved by 7.1%.

Analysis of the results of the speed-strength capabilities of girls based on the results in the standing long jump, the initial indicator was 99.2 ± 11.0 cm. At the end of the second quarter, the girls' result improved by 2.9%. If we take into account that the physical activity of children of this age period is largely associated with jumping and running, then it becomes obvious that the speed and strength qualities of children need to be given close attention in the educational process. A set of developed pedagogical measures aimed at improving the studied motor quality made it possible to significantly improve

them in girls by 11.8%, with a subsequent progressive increase in results in children by the end of the school year by 13.5%.

A significant amount of time was devoted to the strength capabilities of girls, where complexes of simple physical exercises aimed at their strength training were offered during physical education classes.

Analysis of test indicators in the test of flexion and extension of the arms in a lying position, the result was 4.0 ± 1.1 times, respectively. The positive dynamics of the increase in strength abilities in girls is clearly visible in the quarters, where by the end of the second quarter by - 4.7%, in the third by - 11.3% and by the end of the school year the improvement was 22.1% and 18.9%. In girls, a significant increase to 23.1% was revealed. A similar picture is observed in the test of lifting the body from a supine position, where the increase was 20.7%.

Complexly coordinated motor actions such as throwing a tennis ball at a distance were 10.4 ± 3.4 m in girls and boys; at the end of the second quarter, an insignificant improvement in the result by - 0.8 m was noted.

The introduction of focused motor tasks in physical education classes with a training focus and conducted by future physical education specialists made it possible to significantly increase the performance of girls to 12.8 ± 3.9 m, where the increase was 18.8%.

Completing training in the first year, the results of repeated studies confirmed our previously put forward hypothesis that physical exercises focused on the development of necessary motor qualities with a training focus give a significant increase in performance, which is confirmed by an improvement in performance in girls by -23.6%.

The mathematical and statistical processing of the results obtained during the pedagogical experiment with girls of the first year of study in the school education system revealed that girls had the highest coefficient of variation in the flexibility test (54.2%), flexion and extension of the arms in a lying position (42.8%) and lifting the body from a supine position (42.1%). (2.5)

According to physical development data, the highest rank of influence in girls is body weight (27%) and body length (22%). This determined the need to conduct a correlation analysis of indicators of physical development and motor readiness of the study population, providing a scientifically based approach to the set of tools, while identifying valid control standards.

The correlation analysis of the relationship between physical development and motor readiness of girls (Table 3) revealed a connection between speed

indicators in running 30 m and standing long jump, ($r = 0.61$). Weak connection determined between body weight and lifting the body from a supine position ($r = 0.34$), flexion and extension of the arms in a prone position and shuttle running ($r = -0.47$), shuttle running and general flexibility. ($r = 0.34$),

The conducted pedagogical experiment revealed the insufficient level of physical status of children in the first year of education and requires:

- taking into account the individual characteristics of physical development and physical preparedness of children in the first year of education, allowing to determine groups of students according to the level of their motor readiness in the process of conducting physical education lessons;
- normalization of the volume and intensity of physical activity in accordance with the biological needs of the children's body;
- regular medical and pedagogical observations for children's health.

Table 3

Correlation coefficients between indicators of physical development and motor readiness of first-year girls education in the school system

N o.	Name of tests	r	
1.	Running 30 m- shuttle running	0.62	
2.	Running 30 m- long jump	0.61	
3.	Throwing a tennis ball - bending and extending the arms while lying down	0.44	
4.	Flexion and extension of the arms while lying down - shuttle running	-0.52	
5.	Flexion and extension of the arms while lying down - running 30 m	-0.47	-
6.	Shuttle running - general flexibility	-0.38	-
7.	Running 30 m- general flexibility	-0.48	-

The above allows us to conclude that the teaching staff conducting physical education classes with children of primary school age, based on a constant monitoring analysis of their health status, search for effective innovative ways to implement the assigned tasks and timely make appropriate adjustments to the educational process.

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